

Teacher Professional Beliefs and Identity: An Insight into the Professional Development of Primary School Teachers in Pakistan

Bakht Rawan

MPhil (Education), Center for Education and Staff Training, University of Swat, Pakistan

Email: adinbakht@gmail.com

Dr. Nasir Ahmad

Assistant Professor, Center for Education and Staff Training, University of Swat, Pakistan

Email: nasir_cupid@uswat.edu.pk

Dr. Sajjad Hussain

Assistant Professor, Centre for Education and Staff Training, University of Swat, Pakistan

Email: sajjadhussain@uswat.edu.pk

Dr. Nasir Shaheen

Assistant Professor, Centre for commerce and management sciences
University of swat, Pakistan

Email: nasirshaheen@uswat.edu.pk

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Abstract

This research study analyzed the relationship between teacher professional beliefs and identity of primary school teacher for their professional in Pakistan. A representative sample of 342 primary school teachers were randomly selected from all the primary school teachers of District Malakand, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan. Data was collected from sample teachers through a questionnaire developed by the researcher. The questionnaire has been structured into two principal sections, which are professional beliefs and professional identity. The latter section has been further classified into five sub-sections, each representing a distinct aspect of professional identity. These sub-sections include self-esteem, professional commitment, work motivation, task orientation, and job satisfaction. The data collected was analyzed using chi-square and correlation analysis. The study revealed that there is a positive relationship between the teacher's professional beliefs and various components of

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their professional identity. It was recommended that teachers may be provided ample opportunities to enhance their knowledge of professional beliefs and identity, and skills for professional development. These opportunities may be provided through workshops, conferences, and graduate-level coursework.

Keywords: School Teachers, Professional beliefs; Professional identity.

Introduction

Professional beliefs are a set of principles, values, and attitudes of individuals in a specific profession that guide his or her actions, decisions, and behaviors. Professional beliefs serve as a foundation for shaping professional identity, ethical and professional practices of individuals in any profession. In recent years research studies have explored the role of professional beliefs in various fields. A study on professional beliefs of healthcare professionals found that professional beliefs of these professionals were linked to patient care (Keller, 2020; Theisen, 2013). In education, professional beliefs guide teachers' teaching and decisions in the classroom. A recent study by Tan (2020) examined the role of teachers' beliefs in promoting student motivation and engagement and found that teachers who held positive professional beliefs create a supportive classroom environment that fosters student motivation and engagement.

Teachers' beliefs cover diverse range of concepts that act as tool for gaining knowledge and professional development (Zhang, 2020). Beliefs also include personal and non-judgmental aspects that lead to classroom activities (Richards, 1994). It has often been observed that various factors predominantly teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and knowledge influence their teaching approaches. Teachers' beliefs also affect the role of teacher and classroom environment (McClintic, 2015). Professional beliefs and learning process are about teaching and learning are often deeply linked and shape teacher's approach to teaching and classroom management. (Hiebert, 2013; Pajares, 1992). Teachers developed these beliefs through education, personal experiences and training for professional development. (Kyriacou, 2006).

One important aspect of a teacher's professional beliefs is their belief in recognizing himself as a professional teacher. Teachers who have a strong belief in their effectiveness as a teacher can make a difference in the lives of their students and these teachers are likely to take risks in their instruction and use innovative approaches for teaching learning process (Bandura, 1997). Research suggests that student's motivation and academic achievements are the direct outcomes of the association of professional beliefs and teacher efficacy (Tschannen-Moran, 2007). Teachers who prioritize fostering positive relationships with their students create safe and supportive learning environments that motivate students to learn, engage in positive behaviors, develop positive self-concepts, and achieve academic success. Teachers who believe that positive relationships are essential are more likely to create a safe and supportive classroom environment, which can enhance student motivation and engagement (Pekrun, 2009). Teacher's professional beliefs are an essential aspect of their professional identity, which shape their attitude to teaching, classroom management, and relationships with students. It is crucial for teachers to reflect on their beliefs and how they may affect their teaching practices and student outcomes.

Professional identity has been considered the most important component that contributes to teacher's professional development and is defined as "the sense of self and values, beliefs,

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and commitments that shapes professional practice" (Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009). Professional identity is essential for teachers to be effective in their roles. Research studies have revealed that it can have a substantial effect on students, teachers, and education as whole. Teachers who had a strong professional identity were mostly engaged in reflective practices, looking for professional development opportunities, and always committed to their students' success (Dall'Alba, 2006). This commitment to continuous improvement and growth can lead to improved students' learning outcomes.

Professional identity can also lead to increased job satisfaction and teacher retention rates. Darling-Hammond (2017) found that teachers who had strong knowledge of professional identity had more chance to remain in the field, even in challenging environments. On the other hand, a weak professional identity can lead to burnout and attrition. Teachers who are not aware of their professional identity may struggle with feelings of disconnection and lack of purpose, which can lead to feelings of frustration and disillusionment with the profession (Beijaard, 2004).

Establishing a professional identity is a crucial factor for teachers to perform effectively in their respective roles. Teachers who possess a well-established professional identity tend to exhibit higher levels of motivation, engagement, and commitment towards their work. Such teachers have a clear understanding of their professional values, beliefs, and goals, which enables them to consistently enhance their teaching practices (Erikson, 2016).

Research has shown that the professional identity of teachers is closely linked to their instructional practices and their interactions with students (Brock, 2017). Kearney (2017) suggests that teachers who describe themselves as "caring" or "nurturing" are more effective in maintaining constructive relationships with their students. The quality of such relationships can significantly influence both the academic achievements and well-being of students. Moreover, the professional identity of teachers can influence their approach to teaching and their pedagogical choices. When teachers have a clear and established professional identity, they tend to have a stronger sense of purpose and direction in their work. This can lead to greater self-awareness, as well as a deeper understanding of their own teaching practices and the impact these practices have on their students (Ferla, 2014). However, a weak or unclear professional identity can lead to burnout, dissatisfaction, and a lack of commitment to the teaching profession (Fives, 2012).

The professional identity of teachers and professional beliefs are intertwined and play a significant role in the professional development of teachers for better students learning outcomes. Professional identity encompasses a teacher's sense of self as a professional, their beliefs, values, and attitudes towards teaching, as well as their knowledge, skills, and behaviors. Professional beliefs are the set of beliefs that a teacher holds about teaching, learning, and students.

Investigation of primary school teachers' professional identity and beliefs is essential for several reasons. Firstly, knowledge of primary school teachers' professional beliefs and identity can help policymakers and educators develop effective policies and strategies to support and enhance teacher professional development. Teachers who have a sound knowledge of their professional beliefs and identity are more likely to be effective in their roles as teacher, which can significantly affect their teaching and students learning outcomes. Secondly, research on teachers' professional identity and beliefs can help improve teacher

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education and training programs. Teacher education programs can incorporate findings from research to help pre-service teachers develop a strong professional identity and positive beliefs about teaching and learning. Additionally, in-service professional development programs can use research findings to support teachers in developing their professional identity and beliefs continuously. Thirdly, investigation of teacher's professional beliefs and identity can be very beneficial for the development of education system as whole. When teachers possess a strong professional identity and maintain positive beliefs about teaching and learning, they are more likely to demonstrate a higher level of commitment and engagement in their work. As a result, the turnover rates among teachers can decrease, leading to an improvement in teacher retention rates. This, in turn, can have a significant positive impact on the overall quality of education. Therefore, it is essential to conduct research in this area to understand the factors that shape teachers' professional identity and beliefs. Finally, research on teachers' professional identity and beliefs can help us better understand the aspects that affect teachers' professional development and their approach to teaching. By understanding teachers' professional identity and beliefs, we can develop targeted interventions and strategies to support teachers' professional development.

This research aims to investigate the relationship between teacher professional identity and professional beliefs at primary level. The research on teacher professional identity and beliefs aims to enhance our understanding of the intricate relationship between these two factors and their impact on teaching and learning outcomes. By gaining insights into how teachers' professional identity and beliefs shape their practices, we can identify effective strategies to improve the quality of education. The goal of this research was to promote the development of a more effective and equitable education system that provides opportunities to students to succeed in their professional lives.

Research Methodology

This study was Correlational in nature. All (1711) the primary school teachers working in all primary schools of district Malakand constituted the population of the study (EMIS, 2019). A representative sample of 342 primary school teachers were selected from all the primary school teachers of District Malakand, Pakistan using a random sampling method. The sample size was determined based on statistical power analysis to ensure adequate power to detect meaningful correlations. A questionnaire was used to collect data from the participants. The questionnaire has been structured into two principal sections, which are professional beliefs and professional identity. The latter section has been further classified into five sub-sections, each representing a distinct aspect of professional identity. These sub-sections include self-esteem, professional commitment, work motivation, task orientation, and job satisfaction. The questionnaire was pilot tested for reliability. The reliability index of the questionnaire was 0.936, therefore, it was found reliable. Expert opinion was used as a method of estimating the validity of the questionnaire. The data collected was analyzed using correlation analysis and regression analysis. Ethical considerations were taken by obtaining informed consent from the participants, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of the data collected.

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Results

Table1: Professional beliefs and Professional identity

Variables	Mean	S.D	Chi-Value	P-Value
Professional beliefs	2.1433	1.02459	1.410	.000
Self-esteem	1.7661	.97368	3.181	.000
Professional commitment	2.0526	1.10855	3.105	.000
Task orientation	2.1579	1.00362	1.497	.000
Work motivation	2.0409	.95565	1.784	.000
Job satisfaction	2.5936	1.42301	2.046	.000

Table 1 contains data that represents the mean scores and p-values for various dimensions of teachers' professional beliefs and professional identity, including self-esteem, professional commitment, work motivation, task orientation, and job satisfaction. These factors are crucial in modeling the professional identity of teachers, and the data indicates that there is a significant relationship between them.

Table 2

Relationship of Professional identity and professional beliefs of primary school teachers

Professional identity	Professional beliefs	Pearson Correlation
Self-esteem	1	.307**
Professional commitment	1	.304**
Task orientation	1	.155**
Work motivation	1	.293*
Job satisfaction	1	.247**

** Correlation significant at 0.01 levels

Table 2 presents a correlation matrix between different dimensions of teachers' professional identity and professional beliefs, specifically focusing on self-esteem, professional commitment, work motivation, task orientation, and job satisfaction. The data shows that all dimensions of teachers' professional identity and professional beliefs have a positive correlation with each other, indicating that they are positively related. The correlation coefficient ranges from .155** to .307**, which suggests a moderate to strong relationship between these variables.

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Discussions

This study was design to investigate the complex relationship of teacher professional beliefs and identity and the findings suggest that this study has provide valuable insight to this issue in vogue. The major finding of this research was that there is positive relationship between a primary school teacher's professional beliefs and identity. This shows that two components are interdependent and closely linked. The study also identified several specific components of professional identity of teachers that were positively correlated with their professional beliefs. These components include self-esteem, professional commitment, work motivation, task orientation, and job satisfaction. Teachers' professional beliefs and identity are critical components of their professional development and this study prove that they are closely interrelated. Theses finding are consistent with other research studies who has consistently shown that teachers' professional beliefs are closely connected to their professional identity (Hong, 2015; Muijs , 2017).

This study also found that teachers' professional beliefs and self-esteem are closely interrelated. Research studies by Kim, (2018) and Burić (2018) have identified that teachers who have strong professional beliefs have higher levels of self-esteem. The professional beliefs of teacher are the outcome of experiences in the classroom which can be influence by their self-esteem (Hong, 2012; Mehmood, 2011). Teachers who are more professional and confident in their teaching tend to have higher self-esteem than those who struggle or do not have knowledge of professional identity. These teachers face frequent setbacks in their professional lives. On the other hand, low self-esteem can have negative consequences for teachers' well-being and job satisfaction (Yıldırım, 2017).

The study's results also demonstrate a significant and positive correlation between a teacher's professional beliefs and their level of professional commitment. Research studies by Skaalvik, (2014) and Çelikten (2018) have shown that a teacher's professional beliefs are closely connected to their level of professional commitment. Professional commitment is an important factor which can enhance efficiency of teaching process and students learning outcomes (Hightower, 2011).

The study also identified teachers' professional beliefs and work motivation as significantly connected factors that can significantly influence their teaching practices and student learning outcomes. According to Hiebert (2002) teachers' instructional practices and students' learning outcomes are directly influenced by their beliefs. Teachers' professional beliefs about the value and importance of teaching can affect their work motivation (Brouwer, 2018). Professional beliefs along with their levels of job satisfaction, autonomy, and recognition can affect work motivation (Klassen, 2010).

Korthagen (1999) found that teachers who are task-oriented were more likely to have student-centered beliefs confirm that findings of this study that teacher's professional beliefs and their task orientation are positively correlated. A study by Buehl (2015) also validates the finding who sates that primary school teachers' beliefs about teaching and learning were related to their task orientation. Muis (2016) findings that task orientation and primary school teachers' beliefs about intelligence were connected also endorse the findings.

Teachers' professional beliefs and job satisfaction are two important factors that can effect several aspect teacher professional life including professional beliefs, teaching practices, well-being, and retention in the profession. The finding of the study that primary school

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teacher's professional belief and job stultification have positively related endorse the findings by Lortie (1975) who found that teachers' beliefs influenced their job satisfaction and commitment to the profession. The professional beliefs of teachers can influence their sense of fulfillment and purpose that leads to their job satisfaction (Schreiber, 2004). Happiness and contentment with a job shape the perception and attitude of teachers toward teaching as profession. This finding by Skaalvik (2017) also validates the finding. The study concluded that there is a positive correlation between primary school teacher's professional beliefs and their professional identity.

Recommendations

The relationship between teachers' professional beliefs and professional identity is manifold and complex. This study identified this relationship and recommending that further research may be carried out for better understanding of the processes that trigger this relationship. However, supporting teachers in developing a strong professional identity that aligns with their beliefs and values is essential for promoting their well-being, job satisfaction, and ultimately, their ability to provide high-quality education to their students.

Teachers may be provided with opportunities for professional development to improve their knowledge, attitude, skills, and beliefs about teaching. These opportunities can include workshops, conferences, and graduate-level coursework. Recognize and reward effective teaching practices, such as student-centered instruction, differentiated instruction, and formative assessment. Collaboration among teachers can help to promote the sharing of knowledge, experiences, and best practices, which can in turn help to develop teachers' professional beliefs. Schools should provide opportunities for teachers to work together, such as through professional learning communities or teacher-led workshops.

References

1. Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York, NY: Freeman.
2. Beauchamp, C., & Thomas, L. (2009). Understanding teacher identity: An overview of issues in the literature and implications for teacher education. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 39(2), 175-189.
3. Beijaard, D., Meijer, P. C., & Verloop, N. (2004). Reconsidering research on teachers' professional identity. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 20(2), 107-128.
4. Brock, C. (2017). Understanding teachers' professional identities and their relationship to classroom practice: a review of the literature. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 47(2), 206-223.
5. Brouwer, N., Korthagen, F., & Wubbels, T. (2018). Teacher learning in the context of educational change: A review of the literature. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 75, 98-108.
6. Buehl, M. M., & Fives, H. (2015). Exploring teachers' beliefs about teaching and learning: What do teachers believe and how do these beliefs relate to their instructional practices in the classroom? *Teachers College Record*, 117(7), 1-38.
7. Burić, I., & Macuka, I. (2018). The relationship between teacher professional identity and self-esteem: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(4), 1297-1316.
8. Çelikten, M., & Kuzu, A. (2018). Relationship between teachers' professional commitment and their beliefs about teaching and learning. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 13(4), 168-177.
9. Dall'Alba, G., & Sandberg, J. (2006). Unveiling professional development: A critical review of stage models. *Review of Educational Research*, 76(3), 383-412.
10. Darling-Hammond, L., Hyster, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Palo Alto, CA: Learning Policy Institute.

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11. Erikson, L. B. (2016). The Importance of Teachers' Professional Identity for Education: A Review of Literature. *International Journal of Education and Social Science*, 3(5), 22-32.
12. Ferla, J., Valcke, M., & Cai, Y. (2014). Exploring the impact of teachers' beliefs about teaching and learning on their professional identity. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 41, 67-77.
13. Fives, H., & Buehl, M. M. (2012). Spring cleaning for the "messy" construct of teachers' professional identity. *Educational Psychologist*, 47(1), 1-20.
14. Hiebert, J., Gallimore, R., & Stigler, J. W. (2002). A knowledge base for the teaching profession: What would it look like and how can we get one? *Educational Researcher*, 31(5), 3-15.
15. Hiebert, J., Morris, A. K., Berk, D., & Jansen, A. (2013). Preparing teachers to learn from teaching. *Journal of teacher education*, 64(4), 338-350.
16. Hightower, A. M., Work, C. W., Cowen, J. E., Lotan, R. A., & Spinell, A. P. (2011). Teacher commitment, working conditions, and differential incentive policies. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(3), 379-405.
17. Hong, J. Y. (2012). Why do some beginning teachers leave the school, and others stay? Understanding teacher resilience through psychological lenses. *Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice*, 18(4), 417-440.
18. Kearney, A., & Plaxton, N. (2017). The Influence of Teachers' Caring Behaviors on High School Students' Performance, Engagement, and Classroom Behavior. *The High School Journal*, 101(1), 20-36.
19. Keller, T. W., Chauhan, S. P., & Katz, V. L. (2020). Professionalism and physician beliefs: Implications for maternal morbidity and mortality reduction. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 223(5), 654-660. doi: 10.1016/j.ajog.2020.06.035
20. Kim, M., Lee, J., & Lee, J. (2018). The relationship between teacher professional identity, teacher self-efficacy, and teacher self-esteem. *Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 22(3), 173-191.
21. Klassen, R. M., & Chiu, M. M. (2010). Effects on teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction: Teacher gender, years of experience, and job stress. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 102(3), 741-756.
22. Korthagen, F. A. J., & Kessels, J. P. A. M. (1999). Linking theory and practice: Changing the pedagogy of teacher education. *Educational Researcher*, 28(4), 4-17.
23. Kyriacou, C., & Gouling, M. (2006). *The professional development of teachers: Practice and theory*. Routledge.
24. Lortie, D. (1975). *Schoolteacher: A sociological study*. University of Chicago Press.
25. McClintic, S., & Petty, K. (2015). Exploring early childhood teachers' beliefs and practices about preschool outdoor play: A qualitative study. *Journal of early childhood teacher education*, 36(1), 24-43.
26. Mehmood, S., Ahmad, N., & HUSSAN, S. (2011). A study to investigate the relationship between self-esteem and moral judgement. *Interdisciplinary Journal for Contemporary Research*, 6(3), 134-147.
27. Muijs, D., & Reynolds, D. (2017). *Effective teaching: Evidence and practice*. Sage Publications
28. Muis, K. R., Ranellucci, J., Trevors, G., Duffy, M., & Ranellucci, T. (2016). Investigating primary school teachers' beliefs and practices regarding intelligence and effort. *Educational Psychology*, 36(9), 1749-1775.
29. Pajares, F. (1992). Teachers' beliefs and educational research: Cleaning up a messy construct. *Review of Educational Research*, 62(3), 307-332.
30. Pekrun, R., & Elliot, A. J. (2009). Achievement goals and achievement emotions: Testing a model of their joint relations with academic performance. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 101(1), 115-135.
31. Schreiber, J. B., & O'Malley, M. (2004). Professional identity and sense of purpose as resources for professional resilience. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 14(2), 99-107.

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32. Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2014). Teacher self-efficacy and teacher burnout: A study of relations. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 39, 64-72.
33. Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2017). Teacher job satisfaction and motivation to leave the teaching profession: Relations with school context, feeling of belonging, and emotional exhaustion. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, 468-477.
34. Tan, W. J., & Yeo, L. S. (2020). Teachers' belief about effort and its relation to students' motivation and engagement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 112(6), 1276–1288. doi: 10.1037/edu0000406
35. Theisen, J. L., & Sandau, K. E. (2013). Competing beliefs: Nurses' and residents' use of complementary and alternative medicine. *Journal of Holistic Nursing*, 31(3), 178–187. doi: 10.1177/0898010113483834
36. Tschannen-Moran, M., & Woolfolk Hoy, A. (2007). The differential antecedents of self-efficacy beliefs of novice and experienced teachers. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 23(6), 944-956.
37. Yildirim, K. (2017). The relationship between teachers' professional identity and burnout, job satisfaction, and self-efficacy. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 17(5), 1705-1726
38. Zhang, C. (2020). From face-to-face to screen-to-screen: CFL teachers' beliefs about digital teaching competence during the pandemic. *International Journal of Chinese Language Teaching*, 1(1), 35-52.